

NDAC/LO/116
Dec 16, 1988

HIPPARCOS reductions for multiple stars, VIIIb

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As a complement to the results for the 'standard' 8.5 mag case given in Paper VIIIa (NDAC/LO/114), this note gives some SEEKDBL simulation results for systems of magnitude 6.0 and 11.0.

1. Results for mag 6.0

A new series of about 750 2.5 year-simulations has been run for system magnitude $H=6.0$. The ϵ -parameters defined in NDAC/LO/113 were used, presumably giving flat $\Delta\chi^2$ -histograms for single stars (although this was not checked). The frame-level observing time is set at 1 (out of 20) slot(s). These simulated Case History Files were then analyzed by the SEEKDBL program, using the standard mesh (4 points at 0.15 arcsec and 12 points with 0.40 arcsec mesh-size).

With the 't-criterion' discovery level at 1.60 (2% true singles falsely flagged), the statistics of Table 1a is obtained, corresponding to $D_{lim}=4.3$. (As in Paper VIIIa, only separations less than 1.0 arcsec are counted). A decrease of the $\Delta\chi^2$ discovery treshold to $t=0.31$ (25% singles) gives instead the data in Table 1b. Although the increase of D_{lim} is only from 4.3 to about 4.5, there is a substantial gain in the D -interval 4 to 5. Because the bright stars are so few, a 25% flagging-rate for the singles is probably acceptable. Fig 1 shows graphically the discovery-capability of HIPPARCOS for bright doubles. Because no systems with a magnitude-difference larger than 4.5 mag were simulated, the true upper limit for 'resolved' systems is undefined, but in exceptional cases it may probably reach 5.0 mag. Fig. 1 shows also the expected cut-off at about $\rho=1.4$ arcsec. Unknown doubles with larger separations have to be observed from the ground for an approximate position of the secondary.

Fig. 1. All simulated 6.0 mag systems, with the good solutions as filled circles.

Table 1a. Numbers of solutions of different categories in different ranges of D for the 6.0 mag systems, selected for double-star treatment with a 2% t-criterion.

D(mag)	total	sing	probl	bad	good	good/tot(%)
1.0-2.0	20	0	2	1	17	85
2.0-2.5	67	0	4	1	62	93
2.5-3.0	55	0	4	1	49	89
3.0-3.5	105	0	9	2	92	88
3.5-4.0	105	6	8	3	85	81
4.0-4.5	101	14	6	10	50	50
4.5-5.0	118	17	1	3	26	22
5.0-6.0	43	14	2	2	3	7
6.0-	33	13	1	2	0	0

Table 1b. Numbers of solutions of different categories in different ranges of D for the 6.0 mag systems, selected for double-star treatment with a 25% t-criterion.

D(mag)	total	sing	probl	bad	good	good/tot(%)
1.0-2.0	20	0	2	1	17	85
2.0-2.5	67	0	4	1	62	93
2.5-3.0	55	1	4	1	49	89
3.0-3.5	105	0	9	2	93	89
3.5-4.0	105	7	8	3	87	83
4.0-4.5	101	19	6	13	58	57
4.5-5.0	118	43	2	4	52	44
5.0-6.0	43	31	2	2	3	7
6.0-	33	23	1	2	1	3

To see what one may expect to discover after only one year, a second series of about 700 6.0 mag systems were simulated with this shorter observation interval. (The attitude-uncertainties are doubled in the CHF-derivations, as in Paper VIIIa). The solutions were made first as described there, with 4 mesh-points at 0.15 arcsec and 4 points at 0.40 arcsec. As a control, a new set of solutions were made with 4 points at 0.15 arcsec and 12 points with mesh-size 0.30 arcsec. The differences between these sets are rather small, but the second mode was clearly superior, with an acceptable 30% increase of the CPU-time.

The statistics of the solution-quality are made now also in a slightly different manner from the above: Because the only use of the 1-year solution is to give start-values for the secondary position, a 'good' solution is now one with a position-error smaller than 0.30 arcsec and a magnitude difference less than 2.0 mag from the true one. Table 2 gives the statistics for the systems with $\rho < 0.6$ arcsec, and the 25% t-limit 0.31. This corresponds to the surprisingly high D_{lim} -value 4.3, testifying again that one year of observations is enough to discover most of the unknown systems. Fig. 2 shows the solutions in the $\lg \rho / \Delta m$ - plane.

Table 2. Numbers of solutions of different categories in different ranges of D for the '1-year' 6.0 mag systems, selected for double-star treatment with a 25% t -criterion.

$D(\text{mag})$	total	sing	probl	bad	good	good/tot(%)
1.0-2.0	34	0	0	0	34	100
2.0-2.5	55	0	5	0	50	91
2.5-3.0	70	3	13	0	54	77
3.0-3.5	78	2	13	2	61	78
3.5-4.0	87	10	12	3	57	66
4.0-4.5	82	21	3	3	42	51
4.5-5.0	94	35	2	3	12	13
5.0-6.0	20	12	0	1	2	10
6.0-	22	15	0	1	0	0

Fig. 2. Good solutions/all simulations for the 1-year 6.0 mag systems.

2. Results for mag 11.0

The 100 systems of magnitude $H=11.0$ described in Paper VIIIa were augmented by 250 new simulations with the same ϵ -values. (The observing-time is 6 slots per frame, and these simulations take much more CPU-time than the 6-mag runs). The standard solutions (4+12 mesh-points) were made as before, and as reported in Paper VIIIa, the level of the t -criterion is found to influence greatly the total rate of success. Tables 3a and 3b gives the statistics for the extremes with 2% and 100% singles flagged, and the corresponding D_{lim} -values are about 2.0 and 3.3, although these dividing-lines do not fit the observations very well. Fig. 3 shows the latter case, and it is apparent that a larger number of more 'difficult' systems should ideally have been simulated.

Table 3a. Numbers of solutions of different categories in different ranges of D for the 11.0 mag systems, selected for double-star treatment with a 2% t-criterion.

D(mag)	total	sing	probl	bad	good	good/tot(%)
0.0-1.0	40	0	2	3	35	88
1.0-1.5	31	0	1	0	23	74
1.5-2.0	54	0	0	3	38	70
2.0-2.5	72	0	1	3	24	33
2.5-3.0	63	0	0	1	9	14
3.0-3.5	51	0	0	0	1	2
3.5-	5	0	0	0	0	0

Table 3b. Numbers of solutions of different categories in different ranges of D for the 11.0 mag systems, when all the systems are selected, independently of their t-values.

D(mag)	total	sing	probl	bad	good	good/tot(%)
0.0-1.0	40	0	2	3	35	88
1.0-1.5	31	0	3	0	28	74
1.5-2.0	54	2	0	3	49	91
2.0-2.5	72	4	1	7	60	83
2.5-3.0	63	9	1	9	44	70
3.0-3.5	51	16	1	8	26	51
3.5-	5	3	0	2	0	0

Fig. 3. Good solutions/all simulations for the 11.0 mag systems.

A similar series with 350 systems were then simulated for one year of observations, and solved with 4+12 mesh-points, 0.30 arcsec mesh-size. Again, the t -selection is crucial, and Table 4 gives the data when *all* systems are tried. The D_{lim} -value is at 2.8, only some 0.5 magnitude lower than the value for the full observation period. Fig. 4 shows the data graphically.

Table 4. Numbers of solutions of different categories in different ranges of D for the 11.0 mag '1-year' systems. All systems have been run through SEEKDBL.

D(mag)	total	sing	probl	bad	good	good/tot(%)
0.0-1.0	26	0	6	0	20	77
1.0-1.5	27	1	2	1	23	85
1.5-2.0	34	0	3	2	29	85
2.0-2.5	44	7	4	3	30	68
2.5-3.0	38	9	6	4	19	50
3.0-3.5	53	25	2	6	20	38
3.5-4.0	6	4	0	1	1	17
4.0-	6	4	1	1	0	0

Fig. 4. Good solutions/all simulations for the 1-year 11.0 systems.

3. Conclusions

Summarizing the large-scale tests of SEEKDBL made in this report and the last one, we may conclude roughly that the discovery-limit D_{lim} for unknown doubles with small separations ($\rho < 1$ arcsec) is about 4.5 for the brightest systems ($H < 6$), 3.7 for the majority around $H=8-9$, and some 3.0 for the faintest ones ($H > 11$). The corresponding figures after only one year of observations are less than half a magnitude smaller, at least if one considers only systems with $\rho < 0.6$ arcsec. (For larger separations there are many false solutions).

These figures are very encouraging, but there are surely remaining problems. In the present simulations, the true parameters of each double are known, and we may make the separation between 'good' and 'bad' solutions. In reality, the 'bad' ones will be inseparable from the 'good' ones, and more emphasis has to be put on diminishing the 'bad/good'-ratio. This will probably need more simulation efforts, but these should be postponed until some real data and calibrations are available. The main effort will now be directed towards the derivation of the CHF-files.